

Minimal load shedding using the swing equation

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Abstract— Load shedding constitutes the very last resort for preventing total blackouts and cascading events. Conventional load shedding schemes, which are massively applied in industrial practice, adopt a step-wise approach which usually causes over-shedding or fails to prevent frequency decay above the allowable limits. Recently proposed schemes based on real time intelligent control and neural networks achieve the control objective, but fail to minimize the amount of load to be shed due to the delay incurred in consecutive control decisions. This letter proposes a new load shedding scheme, decoupled from the conventional scheme. This scheme, based on the equivalent swing equation of the system, determines the minimal amount of load that should be shed immediately (in a single step) after the load event/disturbance occurs, in order to guarantee system stability.

Index Terms— Frequency stability, load frequency control, load shedding.

I. INTRODUCTION

LOAD shedding is a highly unwanted situation for the electricity consumers, causing significant financial impact. However, it is usually an unavoidable action, taken to prevent the total collapse of the power system. It is essential to minimize the curtailed load, minimizing at the same time the consequences to the customers and the economy. The design of a load shedding scheme is a very challenging, tedious and long term procedure which is usually system specific, requires a large amount of historical data and deep study and understanding of the disturbance events [1,2]. Conventional and contemporary load shedding techniques fail to prevent over-shedding due to the sequence of control and protection actions that need to be taken step-by-step and the inherent time delays introduced [3]. Conventional load shedding schemes are step-wise processes based on prescheduled load shedding tables that are determined based on a rule of thumb and past experience [4]. These tables indicate the amount of load that should be shed at every step depending on the frequency variation.

II. METHODOLOGY

Based on the swing equation and given the ramp up limit and the rated capacity of each committed generating unit, we find the minimum load shedding that ensures that the frequency is always larger or equal than the operator-chosen minimum frequency level, f_{\min}^{req} , that maintains the frequency stability of the system. The proposed scheme is based on the dependence

of the electric frequency on the active power as modeled by the swing equation of the power system

$$2Hf(t) \frac{df(t)}{dt} = p_{mp.u.}(t) - p_{ep.u.}(t) \quad (1)$$

where:

- H is the total normalized inertia constant for the entire system in per unit-seconds (assumed to be known)
- $f(t)$ is the per unit instantaneous electrical frequency of the center of inertia
- $p_{mp.u.}(t)$ is the per unit mechanical power of the turbines
- $p_{ep.u.}(t)$ is the per unit electrical power output of the generators

As soon as a power deficiency between the mechanical power out of the turbines and the electric power out of the generators of magnitude p_d occurs at time $t=t_0$, the electric frequency starts to decline. In response to such a disturbance (e.g., an unexpected outage of a generator) the governor of each unit increases the produced mechanical power to compensate for the disturbance with a ramp limit rate ρ_i for turbine i . The total ramping rate is a monotonically decreasing piecewise-constant function of time, because as time increases different turbines reach their maximum power output p_i^{\max} . Let $t_1 \leq \dots \leq t_i \leq \dots \leq t_N$, with $t_i = (p_i^{\max} - p_i(t_0)) / \rho_i$ denoting the time that generator i reaches its maximum power output and $p_i(t_0)$ the initial mechanical power of turbine i . Let also section i denote the time span between t_i and t_{i-1} . The total ramp rate in section i is

$R_i = \sum_{j=i}^N \rho_j$. The total mechanical power for $t \in [t_{i-1}, t_i]$ can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{mp.u.}(t) &= p_{mp.u.}(t_0) - p_d + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} R_k (t_j - t_{j-1}) + R_i (t - t_{i-1}) \\ &= p_{mp.u.}(t_{i-1}) + R_i (t - t_{i-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Let $f(t^{\min}) = \min_{t \geq t_0} f(t)$, denote the minimum frequency experienced by the system. The optimal amount of load that should be shed, p_{LS}^{OPT} , yields the maximum total demand:

$$p_{ep.u.}(t) = p_{ep.u.}(t_0) - p_{LS}^{OPT}, \quad t > t_0 \quad (3)$$

that maintains stability, i.e. $f(t^{\min}) \geq f_{\min}^{req}$. Although this problem is difficult to solve in the general case due to the piecewise linear nature of $p_{mp.u.}(t)$, considering a section-by-

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section approach with constant load shedding, p_{LS}^{cand} , yields an analytical expression for the frequency of section i , $f_i(t)$. Let $f_i(t_i^{\min}) = \min_{t \geq t_{i-1}} f_i(t)$. The minimum frequency of the system $f(t^{\min})$ is equal to $f_i(t_i^{\min})$ only if $t_i^{\min} \in [t_{i-1}, t_i]$. This is because $p_{mp.u.}(t)$ is a monotonically increasing function of time so that after reaching a frequency minimum, the frequency response will be monotonically increasing. In mathematical terms, the minimum frequency in section i is reached at time t_i^{\min} given by:

$$\left. \frac{df(t)}{dt} \right|_{t=t_i^{\min}} = p_{mp.u.}(t_{i-1}) + R_i(t_i^{\min} - t_{i-1}) - p_{ep.u.}(t_0) + p_{LS}^{cand} = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow t_i^{\min} = t_{i-1} + \frac{p_{ep.u.}(t_0) - p_{LS}^{cand} - p_{mp.u.}(t_{i-1})}{R_i}$$

Analytically solving (1) for section i yields:

$$f_i(t) \frac{df_i(t)}{dt} = \frac{1}{2H} (p_{mp.u.}(t_{i-1}) + R_i(t - t_{i-1}) - p_{ep.u.}(t_0) + p_{LS}^{cand}) \Rightarrow$$

$$\frac{f_i^2(t)}{2} = \frac{1}{2H} \left(p_{mp.u.}(t_{i-1})t + \frac{R_i(t - t_{i-1})^2}{2} - (p_{ep.u.}(t_0) - p_{LS}^{cand})t \right) + C_i$$

Assuming that at time $t=t_0$ the frequency is at its rated value, i.e., $f(t=t_0) = 1$ p.u., the integration constant C_i is given by:

$$C_i = \frac{f_{i-1}^2(t_{i-1})}{2} - \frac{1}{2H} (p_{mp.u.}(t_{i-1})t_{i-1} - (p_{ep.u.}(t_0) - p_{LS}^{cand})t_{i-1}) \quad (6)$$

The quantity p_{LS}^{cand} takes values in the interval $[0, p_d]$. The optimal p_{LS}^{cand} , denoted as p_{LS}^{OPT} , is found using the *bisection method* by repeatedly bisecting the p_{LS}^{cand} interval and selecting the subinterval which ensures that $\min_{t \geq t_0} f(t) \geq f_{\min}^{req}$, as outlined below. The computational complexity of the proposed scheme is $O(N \log(1/\epsilon))$, where ϵ is the optimality tolerance.

Algorithm

While $|P_{LS}^{\max} - P_{LS}^{\min}| \geq \epsilon$

1. $p_{LS}^{cand} = (P_{LS}^{\min} + P_{LS}^{\max})/2$
2. for $i=1 \dots N$
Calculate t_i^{\min} from (4)
if $t_i^{\min} \in [t_{i-1}, t_i]$ then break;
3. Solve (5) for $f_i(t_i^{\min})$ using t_{\min}
4. If $f_i(t_i^{\min}) \geq f_{\min}^{req}$ then $P_{LS}^{\max} = p_{LS}^{cand}$; $P_{LS}^{OPT} = p_{LS}^{cand}$
else $P_{LS}^{\min} = p_{LS}^{cand}$

III. CASE STUDY

The IEEE three generator nine bus test system has been employed to demonstrate the method [4]. It is assumed that f_{\min}^{req} is 48.5 Hz. The ramp rates of generators 1, 2 and 3 are 15, 10 and 8 MW/min respectively. The load disturbance P_d is equal to 50 MW.

Figure 1 depicts the response of the three schemes that are examined: (a) the proposed scheme (b) the conventional load shedding scheme used in practice by several transmission operators [3], and (c) an “ideal” conventional load shedding scheme with optimally designed steps to exactly achieve f_{\min}^{req} .

Figure 1. Response of proposed and conventional load shedding schemes with a 50 MW disturbance and respective required load shedding amount (p_{LS}).

It is deduced that the proposed scheme outperforms the conventional one even when an ideal conventional scheme is used. The proposed scheme achieves a load shedding of 37.42 MW compared to 45.76 MW required by the “ideal” conventional scheme. The extra load shedding required for the conventional load shedding is due to the step wise nature of the scheme and the elapsed time between the decisions (consecutive steps). This time is not present in the proposed scheme since the decision is taken as soon as the disturbance occurs and requires only milliseconds to provide a solution.

It should be stressed that the extra load shedding amount of 8.34 MW (or 22.2% extra load shedding) is the minimum difference that can be achieved between the two schemes. This is because in actual practice there exists a time trip delay associated to each step of the conventional load shedding (from the instant of the load shedding decision to the opening of the circuit breakers). Further, the steps of the conventional load shedding scheme are chosen in a very conservative manner ending up in over-shedding which is accumulated to the above determined quantity and is presented in the figure with the red color. In this scheme the required load shedding amount is 48.57 MW, 11.15 MW or 30% more than the load shedding of the proposed scheme.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A new load shedding scheme is presented that maintains the frequency stability of the grid while achieving a minimal load shedding. The proposed scheme is computationally lightweight and does not present any processing delays due to its analytical nature that allows for a very fast solution. The proposed scheme outperforms the conventional load shedding practice.

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